

Supplemental Materials

Paulson, A.R., S.C. Loughheed, D. Huang, and R.I. Coluatti. 2022. Multi-omics analysis identified symbionts and pathogens of blacklegged ticks (*Ixodes scapularis*) from a Lyme disease hotspot in southeastern Ontario, Canada.

Note: See https://github.com/damselflywingz/tick_microbiome/ for codes and details related to the reproducible analysis pipeline for this study (archived version <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.fqz612jw9>).

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Supplemental Table S1: Core microbiome-associated ASVs detected in this study.

20220502_core_job
11.fasta

>*Rickettsia* sp.

CCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTCGTGCATTAGCGTCAGTTGTAGCCCAGATGACCGCCTTC
GCCACCGGTGTTCTCCTAATATCTAAGAATTTACCTCTACACTAGGAATTCCATCATCCC
CTACTACACTCTAGATTAGTAGTTTTGAAAGCAATTCCGAGGTTAAGCCCCGGGCTTTCAC
TTCCAACCTACTAAACCGCCTACGCACTCTTACGCCAGTAATTCCGAACAACGCTAGCC
CCCTCCGTCT

>*Borrelia miyamotoi*

CCTGTTTGCTCCCTACGCTTTCGTGACTCAGCGTCAGTCTTGACCTAGAAGTTCGCCTTCG
CCTCTGGTATTCTTCTGATATCAACAGATTCCACCCTTACACCAGGAATTCTAACTTCCCC
TATCAGACTCTAGTCATGCAGTTTCCAGCATAGTTCCACAGTTGAGCTGTGGTATTTTACAC
ATAGACTTGCATATCCGCCTACTCACCTTTACGCCAATGATCCCGAACAACGCTCGCCC
CTTACGTATT

>*Borrelia* sp.

CCTGTTTGCTCCCTACGCTTTCGTGACTCAGCGTCAGTCTTGACCCAGAAGTTCGCCTTCG
CCTCCGGTATTCTTCTGATATCAACAGATTCCACCCTTACACCAGAAATTCTAACTTCTC
TATCAGACTCTAGACATATAGTTTCCAACATAGGTCCACAGTTGAGCTGTGGTATTTTATGC
ATAGACTTATATATCCGCCTACTCACCTTTACGCCAATAATCCCGAACAACGCTCGCCC
CTTACGTAT

>*Sphingomonas* sp.

CCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTCGCACCTCAGCGTCAATACATGTCCAGTCAGCCGCCTTC
GCCACTGGTGTTCCTTCCGAATATCTACGAATTTACCTCTACACTCGGAATTCCTACTGACCT
CTCCATGATTCAAGCGATGCAGTCTAAAAGGCAATTCCAGAGTTGAGCTCTGGGCTTTCAC
CTCTTACTTACAAAGCCGCCTACGTGCGCTTACGCCCAGTAATTCCGAATAACGCTAGCT
CCCTCCGTA

>*Pseudomonas* sp.

CCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTCGCACCTCAGTGTCAGTATCAGTCCAGGTGGTTCGCCTTC
GCCACTGGTGTTCCTTCTATATCTACGCATTTACCGCTACACAGGAAATTCACCACCC
TCTACCGTACTCTAGCTTGCCAGTTTTGGATGCAGTTCCAGGTTGAGCCCCGGGGCTTTC
CATCCAACCTTAAACAAACCACCTACGCGCGCTTACGCCCAGTAATTCCGATTAACGCTTGC
ACCCTCTGTATT

>*Anaplasma phagocytophilum*

CCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTCGCACCTCAGCGTCAGTACCGGACCAGATAGCCGCCTTC
GCCACTGGTGTTCCTCCTAATATCTACGAATTTACCTCTACACTAGGAATTCGCTATCCT
CTTCCGACTCTAGTCTGGCAGTATTAAGCAGCTCCAGGGTTAAGCCCTGGCATTTCAC
CTTAACTTACCGAACCAGCCTACATGCCCTTACGCCAATAATTCCGAACAACGCTTGCC
CCCTCCGTATTACC

>*Fronidhabitans* sp.

CCTGTTTCGCTCCCCATGCTTTTCGCTCCTCAGCGTCAGTTACGGCCCAGAGATCTGCCTTC
GCCATCGGTGTTCTCCTGATATCTGCGCATTCCACCGCTACACCAGGAATTCCAATCTCC
CCTACCGCACTCTAGTCTGCCCCGTACCCACTGCAGGCTGGGGGTTGAGCCCCAGATTC
ACAGCAGACGCGACAAACCGCCTACGAGCTCTTACGCCCAATAATTCCGGACAACGCTT
GCACCCTACGTATTAC

>*Mycobacterium* sp.

CCTGTTTCGCTCCCCACGCTTTTCGCTCCTCAGCGTCAGTTACTGCCCAGAGACCCGCCTTC
GCCACCGGTGTTCTCCTGATATCTGCGCATTCCACCGCTACACCAGGAATTCCAGTCTC
CCCTGCAGTACTCCAGTCTGCCCCGTATCGCCCGCACGCCACAGTTGAGCTGTGAGTTTT
CACGAACAACGCGACAAACCACCTACGAGCTCTTACGCCCAGTAATTCCGGACAACGCT
CGGACCCTACGTA

>*Curtobacterium* sp.

CCTGTTTCGCTCCCCATGCTTTTCGCTCCTCAGCGTCAGTTACGGCCCAGAGATCTGCCTTC
GCCATCGGTGTTCTCCTGATATCTGCGCATTCCACCGCTACACCAGGAATTCCAATCTCC
CCTACCGCACTCTAGTCTGCCCCGTACCCACTGCAAGCCCCGAGGTTGAGCCTCGGGATTC
ACAGCAGACGCGACAAACCGCCTACGAGCTCTTACGCCCAATAATTCCGGACAACGCTT
GCACCCTACGTATT

>*Sphingomonas* sp._1

CCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTTCGCACCTCAGCGTCAATACCAGTCCAGTGAGCCGCCTTC
GCCACTGGTGTCTTCCGAATATCTACGAATTTACCTCTACACTCGGAATTCCACTCACCT
CTCCTGGATTCAAGCGATGCAGTCTTAAAGGCAATTCTGGAGTTGAGCTCCAGGCTTTTAC
CTCTAACTTACAAAGCCGCCTACGTGCGCTTTACGCCCAGTAATTCCGAATAACGCTAGCT
CCCTCCGTA

>*Shinella* sp.

CCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTTCGCACCTCAGCGTCAGTAATGGACCAGTAAGCCGCCTTC
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CTTCCATACTCTAGGTACCCAGTATCAAAGGCAGTTCCAGAGTTGAGCTCTGGGATTTTAC
CCCTGACTTAAATACCCGCCTACGTGCGCTTTACGCCCAGTAATTCCGAACAACGCTAGCC
CCCTTCGTATT

>*Williamsia* sp.

CCTGTTTCGCTACCCACGCTTTTCGCTCCTCAGCGTCAGTTACTACCCAGAGACCCGCCTTC
GCCACCGGTGTTCTCCTGATATCTGCGCATTCCACCGCTACACCAGGAATTCCAGTCTCC
CCTGTAGTACTCAAGTCTGCCCCGTATCGCCCGCACGCTTGATGTTAAGCATCAAGATTTCA
CGAACGACGCGACAAACCGCCTACGAGCTCTTACGCCCAGTAATTCCGGACAACGCTCG
CACCTACGTATT

>*Methylobacterium* sp.

CCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTTCGCGCCTCAGCGTCAGTGTCCGGTCCAGTTGGCCGCCTTC
GCCACCGGTGTTCTTCCGAATATCTACGAATTTACCTCTACACTCGCAGTTCCACCAACC
TCTACCGAACTCAAGCCATCCAGTATCGAAGGCAATTCTGTGGTTGAGCCACAGGCTTTCA
CCCCGACTTAAATGGCCGCCTACGCGCCCTTTACGCCCAGTGATTCCGAGCAACGCTAG
CCCCCTTCGTATTAC

>*Acidovorax* sp.

CCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTCGTGCATGAGCGTCAGTACAGGTCCAGGGGATTGCCTTC
GCCATCGGTGTTCTCCGCATATCTACGCATTTCACTGCTACACGCGGAATTCCATCCCC
TCTACCGTACTCTAGCTATACAGTCACAAATGCAGTTCAGGTTGAGCCCAGGGGATTTC
CATCTGTCTTATAAACC GCCTGCGCACGCTTTACGCCAGTAATTCCGATTAACGCTTGC
ACCCTACGTATT

>*Pedobacter* sp.

CCTGTTTCGATCCCCACGCTTTCGTGCCTCAGCGTCAATAGGACCATAGTAAGCTGCCTTC
GCAATCGGTGTTCTGTGACATATCTATGCATTTACCGCTACTTGTACATTCCGCCTACCT
CTAGTCCATTCAAGCCCATCAGTATCAAGGGCACTGCGATGGTTGAGCCACCGTCTTTAC
CCCTGACTTAACAGGCCGCCTACGCACCCTTTAAACCCAATAAATCCGGATAACGCTTGA
TCCTCCGTATT

>*Methylobacterium* sp._1

CCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTCGCGCCTCAGCGTCAGTAATGGTCCAGTTGGCCGCCTTC
GCCACCGGTGTTCTTGCGAATATCTACGAATTTACCTCTACACTCGCAGTTCCACCAACC
TCTACCATACTCAAGCGTCCCAGTATCGAAGGCCATTCTGTGGTTGAGCCACAGGCTTTCA
CCCCGACTTAAAACGCCGCCTACGCGCCCTTTACGCCAGTGATTCCGAGCAACGCTAG
CCCCCTTCGTATT

>*Methylobacterium* sp._2

CCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTCGCGCCTCAGCGTCAGTGTGGTCCAGTTGGCCGCCTTC
GCCACTGGTGTCTTGCGAATATCTACGAATTTACCTCTACACTCGCAGTTCCACCAACC
TCTACCAAACCTCAAGCCAAACAGTATCGAAGGCAATTCTGTGGTTGAGCCACAGGCTTTCA
CCCCGACTTGAATGGCCGCCTACGCGCCCTTTACGCCAGTGATTCCGAGCAACGCTAG
CCCCCTTCGTATTAC

>*Massilia* sp.

CCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTCGTGCATGAGCGTCAATCTTGACCCAGGGGGCTGCCTTC
GCCATCGGTGTTCTCCACATCTCTACGCATTTCACTGCTACACGTGGAATTCTACCCCC
TCTGCCAGATTCAAGCCTTGCACTTTCATCGCAATTCAGGTTGAGCCCAGGGGCTTTCA
CGACAAACTTACAAAACCGCCTGCGCACGCTTTACGCCAGTAATTCCGATTAACGCTTGC
ACCCTACGTATTAC

>*Comamonas* sp.

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GCCATCGGTGTTCTCCGCATATCTACGCATTTCACTGCTACACGCGGAATTCCATCCCC
TCTGCCCACTCTAGCTTTGCAGTCACAAATGGCAGTTCAGGTTGAGCCCAGGGGATTTC
ACCACTGTCTTACAAAACCGCCTGCGCACGCTTTACGCCAGTAATTCCGATTAACGCTTG
CACCTACGTATT

>*Curvibacter* sp.

CCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTCGTGCATGAGCGTCAGTACAGGCCAGGGGATTGCCTTC
GCCATCGGTGTTCTCCGCATATCTACGCATTTCACTGCTACACGCGGAATTCCATCCCC
TCTGCCGTACTCTAGCTATGCAGTCACAAATGCAGTTCAGGTTGAGCCCAGGGGATTTC
ACATCTGTCTTACATAACCGCCTGCGCACGCTTTACGCCAGTAATTCCGATTAACGCTCG
CACCTACGTATT

>*Methyloversatilis universalis*

CCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTCGTGCATGAGCGTCAGTATTGGCCCAGGGGGCTGCCTTC
 GCCATCGGTGTTCTCCACATCTCTACGCATTTCACTGCTACACGTGGAATTCCACCCCC
 TCTGCCATACTCTAGCCGTGCAGTCACAAGCGCAGTTCCCAGGTTAAGCCCGGGGATTC
 ACACCTGTCTTACACAACCGCCTGCGCACGCTTACGCCAGTAATTCCGATTAACGCTCG
 CACCCTACGTATT

>*Hymenobacter* sp.

CCTGTTTCGCTCCCCACGCTGTGCTGCCTCAGCGTCAGTAACAGCCTAGTCAGCTGCCTTC
 GCAATCGGGGTTCTGGACTGTATCTATGCATTTACCCGCTACTCAGTCCATTCCGCCAACC
 TCGTCTGTACTCAAGCCTCACAGTATCCAGGGCAGTTCCGTTGTTGAGCAACGGGGCTTTCA
 CCCC GGACTTATAAGCCGCCTACGCACCCTTTAAACCCAATAAATCCGGACAACGCTCG
 CACCCTCCGTATTACCG

>*Hymenobacter* sp._1

CCTGTTTCGCTCCCCACGCTGTGCTGCCTCAGCGTCAGTAACAGCCTAGTCAGCTGCCTTC
 GCAATCGGGGTTCTGGACTGTATCTATGCATTTACCCGCTACTCAGTCCATTCCGCCAACC
 TCGTCTGTACTCAAGCCCAGTATCCAGGGCAGTTCCGTTGTTGAGCAACGGGGCTTTTC
 ACCCCGGACTTAACGGGGCCGCCTACGCACCCTTTAAACCCAATAAATCCGGACAACGCTC
 GCACCCTCCGTATTACCG

>*Neobacillus* sp.

CCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTCGCGCCTCAGCGTCAGTTACAGACCAGAAAGCCGCCTTC
 GCCACTGGTGTTCCTCCACATCTCTACGCATTTACCCGCTACACGTGGAATTCCGCTTTCC
 TCTTCTGTACTCAAGTCCCCAGTTTCCAATGACCCTCCACGGTTGAGCCGTGGGGCTTTCA
 CATCAGACTTAAAGGACCGCCTGCGCGCGCTTACGCCAATAATTCCGGACAACGCTTG
 CCACCTACGTATTACC

>*Sphingomonas* sp._2

CCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTCGCACCTCAGCGTCAATACCAGTCCAGTGAGCCGCCTTC
 GCCACTGGTGTTCCTCCGAATATCTACGAATTTACCTCTACACTCGGAATTCACCTCACCT
 CTCCTGGATTCAAGCGATGCAGTCTTAAAGGCTATTCCGGAGTTGAGCCCCGGGCTTTCA
 CCTCTAACTTACAAAGCCGCCTACGTGCGCTTACGCCAGTAATTCCGAACAACGCTAGC
 TCCCTCCGTATTACC

Supplemental Table S2: *Rickettsia*-associated ASVs detected in this study.

 20220407_Rickettsia
 _6ASVs.fasta

>*Rickettsia* sp.

CCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTCGTGCATTAGCGTCAGTTGTAGCCCAGATGACCGCCT
 TCGCCACCGGTGTTCTCCTAATATCTAAGAATTTACCTCTACACTAGGAATTCCAT
 CATCCCCTACTACACTCTAGATTAGTAGTTTTGAAAGCAATTCCGAGGTTAAGCCCC
 GGGCTTTCACCTCCAACCTACTAAACCGCCTACGCCTTTACGCCAGTAATTCCG
 AACAACGCTAGCCCCCTCCGTCT

>*Rickettsia* sp._1

CCTGGTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTCGTGCATTAGCGTCAGTTGTAGCCCAGATGACCGCC
TTCGCCACCGGTGTTCCCTCCTAATATCTAAGAATTTACCTCTACACTAGGAATTCCA
TCATCCCCTACTACACTCTAGATTAGTAGTTTTGAAAGCAATTCCGAGGTTAAGCCC
CGGGCTTTCACTTCCAACCTACTAAACCGCCTACGCACTCTTTACGCCCAGTAATTCC
GAACAACGCTAGCCCCCTCCGTCT

>Rickettsia sp._2

CCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTCGTGCATTAGCGTCAGTTGTAGCCCAGATGACCGCCT
TCGCCACCGGTGTTCCCTCCTAATATCTAAGAATTTACCTCTACACTAGGAATTCCAT
CATCCCCTACTACACTCTAGATTAGTAGTTTTGAAAGCAATTCCGAGGTTAAGCCCC
GGGCTTTCACTTCCAACCTACTAAACCGCCTACGCACTCTTTACGCCCAGTAATTCCG
AACAAACGCTCGCCCCCTTACGTATTACC

>Rickettsia sp._3

CCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTCGTGCATTAGCGTCAGTTGCAGCCCAGATGACCGCCT
TCGCCACCGGTGTTCCCTCCTAATATCTAAGAATTTACCTCTACACTAGGAATTCCAT
CATCCCCTACTACACTCTAGATTAGTAGTTTTGAAAGCAATTCCGAGGTTAAGCCCC
GGGCTTTCACATCCAACCTACTAAACCGCCTACGCACTCTTTACGCCCAGTAATTCC
GAACAACGCTAGCCCCCTCCGTCTTACC

>Rickettsia sp._4

CCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTCGCGCCTCAGCGTCAGTTGTAGCCCAGATGACCGCCT
TCGCCACCGGTGTTCCCTCCTAATATCTAAGAATTTACCTCTACACTAGGAATTCCAT
CATCCCCTACTACACTCTAGTCTAGCAGTTTTGAAAGCAATTCCGAGGTTAAGCCTC
GGGCTTTCACTTCCAACCTACTAGACCGCCTACGCGCTCTTTACGCCCAGTAATTCCG
AACAAACGCTAGCCCCCTCCGTCTT

>Rickettsia sp._5

CCTGTTTGCTCCCCACGCTTTCGCACCTCAGCGTCAGTACCGGACCAGATAGCCGCC
TTCGCCACTGGTGTTCCTCCTAATATCTAAGAATTTACCTCTACACTAGGAATTCCA
TCATCCCCTACTACACTCTAGATTAGTAGTTTTGAAAGCAATTCCGAGGTTAAGCCC
CGGGCTTTCACTTCCAACCTACTAAACCGCCTACGCACTCTTTACGCCCAGTAATTCC
GAACAACGCTAGCCCCCTCCGTCTTACC

Supplemental Figure S1: Total abundance of core bacterial amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) associated with *I. scapularis*. Core bacterial community is represented by ASVs with a minimum relative abundance of 0.1 % in at least one V4 16S rDNA sequencing libraries. Sample types are indicated as salivary gland (sg), gut (g), remaining internal viscera (rem) or whole (w) in library names. Other abbreviations: Lemoine Point (LP), Murphy's Point (MP), Queen's University Biological Station (QB), negative control (NC), negative bead (NB), and negative PCR (NP).

Supplemental Table S3: Raw count abundance of *Rickettsia*-associated Amplicon Sequence Variants (ASVs) from batch replicate 16S rRNA libraries.

This file is available at: https://github.com/damselflywingz/tick_microbiome/blob/main/16S_microbiome/figs/Supplemental_Table_S3.xls (archived version <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.fqz612jw9>)

Supplementary Figure S2: Relative abundance of core amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) associated with *I. scapularis* batch PCR replicate libraries (denoted as “a”, “b” and “c” in the library names). Core bacterial community is represented by ASVs with a minimum relative abundance of 0.2 % in at least one V4 16S rDNA library. Sample types are indicated as salivary gland (sg), gut (g), remaining internal viscera (v) or whole (w) in library names. Control samples are indicated as negative bead (NB) and negative PCR (NP) in the library names. Other abbreviations: Lemoine Point (LP), Murphy’s Point (MP), Queen’s University Biological Station (QB), negative control (NC).

Supplemental Table S4: Contaminating ASVs detected using *decontam* R package.

This file is available at: https://github.com/damselflywingz/tick_microbiome/blob/main/16S_microbiome/figs/Supplemental_Table_S4.xls. (archived version <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.fqz612jw9>)

Supplemental Figure S3: Rarefaction curves for V4 16S rDNA sequencing libraries representing the bacterial community associated with whole and dissected *I. scapularis*. Species richness is the total number of amplicon sequence variants detected in each library. Sample types are indicated as salivary gland (sg), gut (g), remaining internal viscera (rem) or whole (w) in the library names. Control sample is indicated as negative bead (NB).

Supplemental Table S5: *Babesia* apicoplast sequence detected (“ASV7”).

20220407_ASV7.fast

a

>Bacteria (kingdom)

```
CCCATTTGCTACTTTAGCTTTCATCTATCAATGTCAGATATAAACTAGTTTAATACTT
TCGTTTATGGCCTTCTTTAATGTATATAAATCATATTTCCACCATTATTCAAAAAATTC
CTTAAACTTATTTTACTCTCAAGTTTATTAATATTAATTTAATGTTTAAAAATATTA
TTTTAAATTTATAATATAATAGAATAAACCATCTAAAGATGCTTTATGCCCAATAA
TTGTGAATAACGCTTATATCCTCTGTATTACC
```

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Supplemental Figure S4: Phylogenetic reconstruction for partial apicoplast sequence of *Babesia* spp. detected in the microbiome of *I. scapularis* by BLAST pairwise alignments, fast minimum evolution tree method with max sequence difference of 75 %.

Supplemental Figure S5: Phylogenetic reconstruction of V4 16S rDNA sequences from *A. phagocytophilum* target ASV6 detected in the microbiome of *I. scapularis* in this study; 11 sequences from *A. phagocytophilum* strains and *Ehrlichia* spp. in the GenBank 16S rRNA reference database; and two *A. phagocytophilum* strains previously collected in Canada (Krakowetz *et al.* 2014). The bootstrap confidence is reported for internal nodes values greater than 65 % out of 1,000.

Supplemental Figure S6: Phylogenetic reconstruction of V4 16S rRNA DNA sequences from *Borrelia* targets ASV2 and ASV2 detected in the microbiome of *I. scapularis*, 27 sequences from *Borreliella/Borrelia* spp. in the GenBank 16S rRNA reference database. Note that 16S rDNA gene sequence is not available for *Borreliella kurtenbachii*. The bootstrap confidence is reported for internal nodes values greater than 65 % out of 1,000.

Supplemental Figure S7: LEfSe analysis of tick microbiome for discriminating ASVs associated with A) whole-tick (w), or dissected (d) salivary glands, guts, or remaining viscera samples across three sampling sites; and B) w or d tick samples at specific sites. The ASVs were agglomerated at the lowest taxonomic level; N = 419 (see methods). Sampling location abbreviations: Lemoine’s Point (LP), Murphy’s Point (MP) and Queen’s University Biological Station (QB).

Supplemental Figure S8. Relative abundance of unique ASVs detected either from whole (W) *I. scapularis* or dissected (D) salivary glands (see Figure 3B in the main paper). Sample types are indicated in the library names as salivary gland (sg), gut (g), internal viscera (rem) or whole (w). Location abbreviations: Lemoine's Point (LP), Murphy's Point (MP) and Queen's University Biological Station (QB).

Supplemental Figure S9: Pairwise comparison (Comp) of unweighted UniFrac distances between tick-associated bacterial communities for within and between sample types of dissected (d) tissues or whole-body (w).

Supplemental Figure S10: Repeated analysis with the top 500 most abundant amplicon sequence variants (ASVs). A) Pairwise comparison (Comp) of unweighted UniFrac distances between tick-associated bacterial communities for within and between sample types of dissected (d) tissues or whole-body (w). B) Principle co-ordinates analysis based on unweighted UniFrac distance metric ASVs detected from *I. scapularis* using V4 16S rDNA sequencing. The tissue types are indicated in the library names as either dissected (d): salivary gland (sg), gut (g), remaining (rem) internal viscera, or whole (w). Location abbreviations: Lemoine's Point (LP), Murphy's Point (MP) and Queen's University Biological Station (QB).

Supplemental Table S6 – illumina_nextera.fa

illumina_nextera.fa.
txt

```
>Illumina_D5_adapter_i5a
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>Illumina_D5_adapter_i5b
ACACTCTTTCCCTACACGACGCTCTTCCGATCT
>Illumina_D5_adapter_i7a
GATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTCAC
>Illumina_D5_adapter_i7b
ATCTCGTATGCCGTCTTCTGCTTG
>Truseq_Universal_Adapter
AATGATACGGCGACCACCGAGATCTACACTCTTTCCCTACACGACGCTCTTCCGATC
T
>Truseq_Adapter_1a
GATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTCAC
>Truseq_Adapter_1b
ATCTCGTATGCCGTCTTCTGCTTG
>Illumina_D5_adapter_i5a Reversed:
GTGTAGATCTCGGTGGTCGCCGTATCAT
>Illumina_D5_adapter_i5b Reversed:
AGATCGGAAGAGCGTCGTGTAGGGAAAGAGTGT
>Illumina_D5_adapter_i7a Reversed:
GTGACTGGAGTTCAGACGTGTGCTCTTCCGATC
>Illumina_D5_adapter_i7b Reversed:
CAAGCAGAAGACGGCATACGAGAT
>Truseq_Universal_Adapter Reversed:
AGATCGGAAGAGCGTCGTGTAGGGAAAGAGTGTAGATCTCGGTGGTCGCCGTATCA
TT
>Truseq_Adapter_1a Reversed:
GTGACTGGAGTTCAGACGTGTGCTCTTCCGATC
>Truseq_Adapter_1b Reversed:
CAAGCAGAAGACGGCATACGAGAT
```

>TruSeq_Universal_Adapter

AATGATACGGCGACCACCGAGATCTACACTCTTTCCCTACACGACGCTCTTCCGATC
T

>Nextera_XT

CTGTCTCTTATACACATCT

>Nextera_XT_Reverse

AGATGTGTATAAGAGACAG

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